

TECH4EU CONSTRUCTION

**TO DEVELOP AND DEMONSTRATE NEW
TECHNOLOGIES TO DIGITALISE FURTHER
AND AUTOMATISE THE EUROPEAN
CONSTRUCTION SECTOR**

Funded by
the European Union

DISCLAIMER

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The projects that form the Tech4EUConstruction Cluster have received funding from the European Union's H2020 and Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under the following Grant agreements:

N. 101058548 (Beeyonders)

N. 958398 (Bim2Twin)

N. 955356 (Heron)

N. 101058236 (HumanTech)

N. 101069610 (Incube)

N. 101058580 (Reconmatic)

N. 101056773 (Reincarnate)

N. 101058731 (Robértarmé)

TABLE OF CONTENTS

▶	About the cluster	6
▶	BEEYONDERS	8
▶	HumanTech	10
▶	InCUBE	12
▶	Reconmatic	14
▶	Reincarnate	16
▶	RoBétArmé	18

ABOUT THE CLUSTER

The Tech4EUConstruction cluster unites eight European projects advancing AI and robotics in construction. Supported by the European Commission, it fosters collaboration to drive digitalization, automation and innovation.

The cluster enhances safety, working conditions, and industry appeal while strengthening Europe's technological independence.

KEY FACTS

24

Months of intensive collaboration
from June 2023

8

Projects involved

152

Partners

OUTCOMES

- ▶ Organisation of joint webinars
- ▶ Successful presence at the European Robotic Forum with annual workshops on AI and Robotics
- ▶ Joint presence in major EU and international events
- ▶ Multiple joint social media campaigns
- ▶ Collaboration in human-robot interaction activities, with particular focus on gender representation in the sector.

CLUSTER MEMBERS

Note: this brochure presents the projects that are still active.

For more information about Bim2Twin and Heron, please visit their websites at:

<https://bim2twin.eu/> and <https://www.heron-h2020.eu/>

Breakthrough European technologies Yielding construction sovereignty, Diversity & Efficiency of Resources

▶ **COORDINATED BY**
Antonio Alonso Cepeda (ACCIONA)

▶ **PARTNERS**
21 (ACCIONA, PNO, ITA, TECNALIA, ICONS, CATEC, STAM, IIT, EBC, CSTB, HI-DROMEK, INFRA PLAN, AISCAT, DTU, VTT, CAIDIO OY, FIRA, COBOD, SEABOOST, INGEO BV, HOLCIM)

▶ **DURATION**
June 2022 - November 2025

BEEYONDERS aims to produce, commercialise and integrate pioneering worker-friendly technologies to address key industry needs of the European Construction sector.

The project focuses on developing, testing, and demonstrating innovative solutions that enhance efficiency, safety, and sustainability on construction sites.

At the heart of BEEYONDERS lies the adoption of advanced technologies such as autonomous and collaborative robotics, additive manufacturing, and a digital twin.

These tools will:

- ▶ Improve productivity and cost efficiency while reducing waste and CO₂ emissions.
- ▶ Enhance the safety and well-being of workers, ensuring inclusivity across age and gender.
- ▶ Support European independence from foreign technologies, fostering a robust and competitive industry.

CONCEPT & OBJECTIVES

“We are going to develop technology for a better, more efficient, less polluting and more human construction sector; following the best European standards and values”

Antonio Alonso Cepeda
BEEYONDERS project coordinator.

<https://beeyonders.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/beeyonders/>

<https://www.youtube.com/@beeyondersEU>

BEEYONDERS is set to transform the construction industry across economic, environmental, and societal dimensions. By integrating advanced technologies, the project aims to improve production efficiency by 14%, reduce CO₂ emissions by 11% through sustainable practices, and enhance worker safety and wellbeing. This will result in a 50% decrease in injury-related sick leaves and a 20% increase in worker endurance.

These goals will be explored through six pilot scenarios, supported by an AI-driven Digital Twin platform, aiming to deliver tangible improvements in operations, sustainability, and the overall well-being of workers:

- ▶ **Building Construction:** Wearables, drones, and exoskeletons will reduce idle times by 8.3% and lower injury risks.
- ▶ **Maritime Construction:** Optimized caisson designs will cut mortar use and CO₂ emissions while fostering marine biodiversity through bio-inspired structures.
- ▶ **Road Construction:** Autonomous vehicles and Digital Twin technology will streamline earthwork planning, saving fuel and reducing emissions.
- ▶ **Tunnel Construction:** Autonomous robotic solutions will minimize downtime by clearing debris and conducting safety checks immediately after blasting.
- ▶ **Road Maintenance:** Robotics will perform maintenance without disrupting infrastructure use.
- ▶ **EU-Japan Collaboration:** Partnering with Giken Ltd, the project will enhance press-in piling with a Digital Twin, enabling real-time adjustments and boosting environmental performance.

RESULTS & IMPACT

Human-centred technologies for a safer and greener construction industry

▶ **COORDINATED BY**
Jason Rambach (DFKI)

▶ **PARTNERS**
22 organisations from Europe, Switzerland, Japan, and Norway

▶ **DURATION**
June 2022 - June 2025

HumanTech is a groundbreaking initiative that proposes to use human-centered technologies to advance the European construction industry — increasing the safety and wellbeing of its workforce, improving its productivity, and making it greener and resource-efficient. Also, it will allow inventory the materials used in buildings, facilitating their reuse and recycling.

From wearables (exoskeletons, cameras, XR glasses) for workers' protection and support, to robots that can collaborate with humans while contributing to the green transition of the industry.

The project aims to achieve major advances in these technologies and thus disrupt how construction is carried out by a new generation of highly skilled workers and engineers working in a digital, safe, and rewarding environment. On the other hand, to help create a green, circular, and more efficient construction industry, it is necessary to decrease error-prone manual labor and increase fabrication precision.

This can be achieved through automation, with technologies that enable precise processes and optimised use of building materials — which they will develop in this project. These also allow for an inventory of materials used in buildings, facilitating their reuse and recycling.

So, through this project, they will also be able to advance circularity in this sector, significantly reducing resource waste and greenhouse gas emissions.

CONCEPT & OBJECTIVES
MAIN OBJECTIVES

<https://humantech-horizon.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/humantech-eu/>

https://x.com/HumanTech_EU

<https://www.youtube.com/@humantecheu>

The HumanTech project has achieved several significant milestones in its mission to enhance the European construction industry through human-centered technologies.

Advancements in Robotics and AI

The project has made notable progress in integrating robotics and artificial intelligence into construction processes, as demonstrated in the project pilots:

- ▶ Robotic systems capable of grasping and handing over materials, enhancing human-robot collaboration.
- ▶ Teleoperated applications for precision tasks, such as mastic application, improving efficiency and worker well-being.
- ▶ Extended Reality (XR) technologies that overlay Building Information Modeling (BIM) data over real-world structures, facilitating digitized progress tracking and project management in construction.

Scientific Recognition

HumanTech's commitment to scientific excellence is evident through multiple awards and publications:

- ▶ First-place awards in three categories at the Benchmark on Object Pose challenge 2023 during the International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV) 2023.

Third place in the Scan-to-BIM challenge at the Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR) 2023.

14 scientific publications in prestigious conferences and journals, including CVPR, ICCV, RA-L.

Open-access resources: The project has made several resources publicly accessible, such as:

- ▶ Public deliverables from the first 18 months.
- ▶ Source code repositories for various scientific publications.
- ▶ Micro-learning units and datasets, supporting ongoing research and education in construction technologies.

RESULTS & IMPACT

An INCLUsive toolBox for accElerating and smartening deep renovation

▶ COORDINATED BY

CERTH (Greece)

▶ PARTNERS

23 Partners from Greece, France, Italy, Spain, Belgium, Poland & Netherlands

▶ DURATION

July 2022 - July 2026

InCUBE envisions to unlock the EU renovation wave through cutting-edge standardised and integrated processes based on industrialisation, innovative renewable energy technologies, digitalisation, and new market entrants.

All while accounting for social inclusion, gender mainstreaming and upskilling of current and potential workforce.

The solutions emerging from InCUBE will be validated in 3 large-scale demo sites: Zaragoza (Spain), Trento (Italy) and Groningen (Netherlands).

CONCEPT & OBJECTIVES

<https://incubeproject.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/incube-project-eu/>

<https://x.com/incubeeu>

InCUBE applies multiple technologies and connects relevant stakeholders, facilitating seamless information and data exchange under the umbrella of Internet of Things-driven smart technologies. This approach unlocks and offers new, smarter, and more tailored services.

The project is structured around four key pillars: process innovations that support the industrialisation of renovation, product innovations that promote the utilisation of new materials, software innovations that enable the digitalisation of products and processes, and business innovations that facilitate the entry of new market players.

InCUBE addresses several critical needs of the EU community, including the market uptake of sustainable materials to support deep renovation and workflow optimisation, the development of significantly improved integrated solutions for renovation phases, and the better integration of building information across the entire life cycle to enhance decision-making for high energy performance and user comfort.

It also aims to make deep renovation more appealing and affordable for all stakeholders, transform buildings and their users into active nodes of the energy system, and strengthen the connection between different actors in the construction value chain to facilitate knowledge exchange.

Additionally, InCUBE supports more renovation demonstrations across the EU, including those involving cultural heritage buildings, and enhances the construction sector's capability to be inclusive and oriented toward people's needs.

RESULTS & IMPACT
EXPECTED

Automated Solutions For Sustainable And Circular Construction And Demolition Waste Management

- ▶ **COORDINATED BY**
Czech Technical University (Prague)
- ▶ **PARTNERS**
23 partners from 7 countries (5 EU + UK + China)
- ▶ **DURATION**
July 2022 - June 2026

RECONMATIC is a European research and innovation project that explores automated solutions for sustainable construction and demolition waste (CDW) management. It focuses on integrated decision-making tools that would help identify and minimise waste during the entire lifecycle of a building.

The project, funded by Horizon Europe and UK Research and Innovation (UKRI), aims to create solutions that can be easily adopted by all stakeholders involved in CDW processes.

Main Objectives:

- ▶ Develop, test, and promote digital tools for material tracing and C&D waste management using existing databases.
- ▶ Create automated solutions for deconstruction and waste separation.
- ▶ Implement cross-sector solutions for various materials, covering construction, waste management, and transportation.
- ▶ Demonstrate reuse, recycling, and transformation solutions at four European sites.
- ▶ Evaluate the solutions' economic, environmental, and societal impact, including cost savings and CO₂ reduction.
- ▶ Develop learning resources and contribute to standards, policies, and best practices.

CONCEPT & OBJECTIVES

<https://www.reconmatic.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/reconmatic/>

<https://x.com/reconmatic>

https://www.youtube.com/@RECONMATIC_Project

- ▶ Digital Information Management System (DIMS) to integrate all stages of construction and demolition waste (CDW) management, ensuring waste traceability and full life-cycle asset information.
- ▶ Automated deconstruction and waste separation solutions to improve efficiency, considering material deliveries, site conditions, and logistics.
- ▶ Blockchain-driven waste tracking to enhance transparency, securing the information flow between suppliers, contractors, sites, and carriers.
- ▶ Guidelines and methodology for a Materials Data Bank (MDB) to serve as a national repository for waste and recycling data from manufacturers and their products.
- ▶ Prediction tools integrated into BIM to forecast waste generation, recycling, and recovery costs based on project-specific inputs. WASTEie dataset development to support BIM-driven technologies for enhanced waste management.
- ▶ Generative design methodology using advanced industry tools to optimize waste reduction in the design phase.
- ▶ Semi-mobile robotic sorting prototype that combines the best existing and newly developed technologies for efficient, cost-effective CDW separation.
- ▶ RECONMATIC will deliver 6 demonstrations, to be carried out in 5 European countries (Greece, Italy, Czech Republic, Spain, United Kingdom), that will each pilot technologies on building and infrastructure projects covering different stages of the project lifecycle.

**RESULTS & IMPACT
EXPECTED**

Innovative solutions for a greener construction industry

▶ COORDINATED BY

Technische Universität Berlin (Germany)

▶ PARTNERS

16 organizations from 6 EU Member States, Serbia and China

▶ DURATION

June 2022 - May 2026

<https://www.reincarnate-project.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/reincarnate-eu/>

<https://x.com/ReincarnateEU>

<https://www.youtube.com/@reincarnateeu>

CONCEPT & MAIN OBJECTIVES

Reincarnate is transforming the **construction industry** by implementing **technical and social innovations to advance circular economy practices**.

By focusing on extending the lifecycle of building products, elements, and materials through reuse and recycling, the project aims to **reduce construction and demolition waste**.

Main Objectives:

- ▶ Maximize the cumulative virtues of a building, a building product, or a building material during its life.
- ▶ Establish a transparent track record of these virtues.
- ▶ Use this track record to ensure that a building, building product, or building material can be reused at a high quality in an afterlife.

Central to the project's effort is the development of the **Circular Potential Assessment Information Management Platform (CP-IM)**, a digital tool designed to **assess and enhance the circular potential of construction materials**. Employing advanced methodologies such as digital twin representation, artificial intelligence, and robotic automation, Reincarnate seeks to validate and promote the **reusability of materials and products in the construction sector**, thus encouraging circularity and sustainability.

Along with the CP-IM, Reincarnate introduces **10 technical and process innovations** that extends existing information and communication technologies methods and innovations from low technology readiness levels (TRL 1-4) to proven technical solutions at the system or the sub-system level (TRL 6), that are **being validated in real demonstration projects**.

Reincarnate aims to achieve an **80% reduction in construction and demolition waste** by introducing circular practices and increasing the reuse of construction products. With a goal of **improving the reusability of materials by 50%**, Reincarnate ensures that resources are repurposed effectively, reducing dependency on raw materials and minimizing environmental harm.

In addition to waste reduction, the project aims to **develop new value chains and sustainable business models** that bring together cross-sectoral actors. By fostering collaboration between demolition companies, architects, and construction companies, Reincarnate is creating a more integrated and sustainable approach to construction. The implementation of material tracking systems and modular dismantling techniques further enhances **transparency and resource efficiency across the value chain**.

Ultimately, the project will deliver replicable, **climate-neutral solutions for the construction sector**, enabling stakeholders to adopt circular practices that reduce waste, lower carbon emissions, and support sustainable growth.

RESULTS & IMPACT EXPECTED

Human-robot collaborative construction system for shotcrete digitization and automation through advanced perception, cognition, mobility and additive manufacturing skills

▶ COORDINATED BY

Dr. Dimitrios Giakoumis (CERTH)

▶ DURATION

June 2022 - November 2025

▶ PARTNERS

19 partners from 12 European countries

Context: According to the World Economic Forum, the construction industry currently accounts for about 6% of the global GDP (Gross Domestic Product) and is expected to reach around 14.7% in 2030, which means that the construction sector plays a key role in any country's economy.

At European level, construction is a strategically important sector for the economy involving a wide range of stakeholders and companies, providing 18 million jobs.

The importance of construction automation has grown rapidly worldwide. This need is mainly driven by the shortage and rising costs of skilled workers, the tremendous increased needs for new infrastructures to serve the daily activities and the immense demand for maintenance of ageing infrastructure.

To achieve the desired level of automation, analogous to the Industry 4.0, breakthrough technologies such as sensors, augmented reality systems, high-performance computing, additive manufacturing, advanced materials, autonomous robots and simulation systems, have been adapted for construction applications and this transformation has been called as Construction 4.0.

The RobétArmé project targets the development of a human-robot collaborative construction system for the shotcrete digitalization and automation through advanced perception, cognition, mobility and additive manufacturing skills that can operate in diverse construction environments.

To this end, RobétArmé will deliver collaborative construction mobile manipulators, consisting of an:

- ▶ Inspection-Reconnaissance mobile manipulator (IRR) to address fast, high precision modelling and rebar reinforcement through metal additive manufacturing in the preparatory phase
- ▶ Shotcrete and Finishing mobile manipulator (SFR) to address autonomous shotcrete application and surface finishing during the construction and finishing phase, respectively.

CONCEPT &
MAIN OBJECTIVES

<https://www.robotarme-project.eu/>

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/robotarmeproject>

<https://x.com/robotarme>

The main objectives of the project are:

- ▶ To develop a **cognitive robot platform**, that address the complete chain of shotcrete application for autonomous construction, maintenance and monitoring activities of infrastructures.
- ▶ To develop an **advanced high-precision and real-time infrastructure perception system** through AI-enabled technologies and multimodal sensor fusion
- ▶ To develop cognitive and adaptable **human-robot collaboration control schemes** for dexterous execution of construction and maintenance tasks
- ▶ To release **advanced modelling tools** tailored to the Building and Construction Information Models (BIM) for the fast and greener implementation of automated construction activities
- ▶ To develop **cognitive Digital Twin and simulation environments** for construction monitoring, diagnostics and orchestration activities

The RoBétArmé project will deliver digitalization and robotics solutions in the three phases of shotcrete application as follows:

- ▶ Inspection and Preparatory Phase
- ▶ Construction and Repair Phase
- ▶ Surface Finishing Phase

The RoBétArmé project targets the automation of shotcrete application in four use case scenarios of diverse construction sites, including:

- ▶ Construction of ground support walls
- ▶ Repair of piles/beams
- ▶ Repair of bridges posttensioned boxes
- ▶ Construction of culverts or tunnels

**RESULTS & IMPACT
EXPECTED**

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